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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 1

Pages: 30-39

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2239

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13356020

Manuscript Accepted: 07-20-2024

Lived Experiences of Professionals Working from Home: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

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Abstract

The current study is about the lived experiences of professionals working from home and how it's affecting their work productivity and well-being. Interpretative phenomenological analysis design was utilized in this study and purposive sampling was used for the respondents. Seven professionals from various fields of work in Metro Manila were the respondents of the research, all of them working full-time work from home, which also serves as the homogeneity that is needed for this chosen research design. Interviews through Zoom were conducted in order to acquire the information relevant to the study. The researchers utilized a researcher-made 15-item open-ended questionnaire that was validated by experts in the field of research and psychology as a theme, workplace productivity while working from home, the impact of working from home on well-being, and the importance of having a dedicated workplace at home. The results also concluded that the work-from-home setup had both positive and negative effects on employees. It gives employees a convenient working environment that allows them to work flexibly. In such settings, however, employees also tend to feel isolated and technologically inadequate. Employees tend to be more productive in WFH settings.

Keywords: *work from home, productivity, well-being, remote work*

Introduction

This pandemic has changed the way we look at work. It gave us a new outlook on how work should be done in the future. One of the most notable benefits of this new normal was the ability to work remotely. In a study that was conducted by Haridas et al. (2021), the researchers concluded that the productivity of the workers still depends on the worker's nature of the business. So, while certain workplaces can easily adapt to the Work From Home setup, some businesses must also work together with their employees to create an environment that is more inclusive and less disruptive. Nowadays, employees wish to work from home, particularly those who do not want to get up in the morning, shower, and get ready to drive to the workplace, where they will be trapped in heavy traffic and waste time. Businesses and workplaces have begun to adjust to working from home while almost a third of the world is on lockdown. Another aspect that adds to the increased workload is being adapted to working remotely. Employees are working longer hours, and those who do not have a separate office space are finding it harder to strike a work-life balance. Although it is unclear whether WFH was sought before the pandemic to attain a better work-life balance, it is now widely employed as a virus prevention approach.

The Work From Home setup has been very beneficial to the employees for it gives them time flexibility. Because of this benefit, they are able to manage their time more efficiently and make effective and quick decisions with regard to their work duties. According to Bloom et al. (2014), the Work From Home arrangement has benefited employees because it has resulted in a large improvement in productivity, which can be linked to a more pleasant working environment at home. Another reason, according to the researchers, is that people are more productive at home. Remote workers can enjoy the benefits of working from home, such as not having to worry about getting sick.

However, it is also said that one of the disadvantages of this setup is that working from home might not be suited to everyone's personality, ability, and lifestyle. According to Galanti et al. (2021), one of the disadvantages of WFH setup is being around family members. Working from home may not be suitable for everyone's lifestyle, for example, some people may have young children who are oblivious to boundaries and can cause disruptions during working hours. The presence of spouses and children (especially if still in childhood) involved in work and school activities at home, the interruption of child-care and education services observed during the pandemic, and having to participate in household duties all had a significant impact on distant workers. Aside from that, according to a study that was conducted by Bhatia et al. (2019), the researchers noted that one of the disadvantages of the work from home setup, as mentioned by the participants, is data and security breaches since the employees are working remotely, the company's information is very susceptible to security threats and hacking.

People might not prefer the work from setup and still prefers working onsite, because one of the major problems of those work from is an instead less stressful environment, just like on-site unfortunately work from home did not lessen the burden of employees according to Svensson (2021) that work from setting only give a negative impact on employees' mental health. Most especially at this time we are in a pandemic. Even though one year has passed since the pandemic started, all of us are still in the adjustment process or not all the people have already accepted our new normal today. The problem of mental health capacity doesn't have enough evidence because of the lack of studies regarding that problem, given that work from home had been practiced during this pandemic so the studies are expected to be limited research on the problem of mental health.

This study makes it easier for employers to explore and support workers' efficacy and work-life balance after they work from home.

This research presented insights into employees' life narratives regarding their work from home experience and how it is affecting their productivity and overall well-being. This determined the specific needs of those who are working from home, on how organizations can help and acknowledge the concerns of their employees.

Since the majority of the previous studies have been conducted prior to the beginning of the pandemic – in which previous researchers have only covered jobs and employees that are already in a work from home setup– the aim of this study is to get a clear perspective on how the certain workforces that aren't previously in a remote setup, have adapted to the shift to Work From Home and how they are currently implementing this setup. Furthermore, this study also provides some knowledge on how it's affecting the employee's performance and engagement, by presenting the advantages and disadvantages of the work from home setup through the employee's lived experiences.

And lastly, this research provides a substantial viewpoint on how employers can better implement certain rules and regulations for the Work-From-Home Setup and how to support their employees' specific needs relating to the work from home setup. The data was gathered thru an online Zoom meeting where the researchers presented an open-ended interview questions to the respondents regarding their work from home experience. The results of the open-ended interviews and questionnaires were collected and evaluated to find relevant trends and data points.

Research Questions

This study determined and further explored the lived experiences of professionals who are working from home and its impact on the performance and well-being of the employees. Specifically, it answered the central question of this study which is:

1. How the Work-From-Home Setup affects the employees' productivity and well-being?

Literature Review

Working from home expands the number of options available to employers in terms of how they can operate and structure themselves. Since the COVID-19 pandemic started, work-from-home setup has provided some companies the flexibility they need to keep their businesses running while prioritizing the health and well-being of their employees. Many companies, even before the pandemic, have already recognized its benefits to their businesses and how it improved work-life balance for their employees. Employees and employers have praised the work-from-home setup for offering a better work-life balance. The WFH setup, as a work arrangement, allows employees to accomplish their jobs and activities outside of the office, providing them with greater liberty. With the ability to choose where to work and how to balance work and personal life (Reyes & Carlier, 2021).

As mentioned in a study conducted by Bhatia et al. (2021), the Work From Home setup has been very beneficial to the employees for it gives them time flexibility. Because of this benefit, they are able to manage their time more efficiently and make effective and quick decisions with regard to their work duties. Workplace flexibility is typically considered to be the ability of workers to make choices influencing when, where, and how long they are engaged in the task. It is very important to have employees during their off-time because working long hours can affect their productivity. It was also stated in a study conducted by Ritsu et al. (2021) that the key benefit of the work-from-home setup is its strong association with greater mental health. Some of the potential benefits said in this study is that it “facilitates a greater focus on work” and “Less fatigue and having a healthier condition”. Some participants also answered that having this setup can definitely give them more time to rest, for they would no longer have to commute to work.

According to a study conducted by Jun Yu and Yihong Wu (2021), almost half of the employees have switched to the new set-up, which is working from home, and some of the employees are not satisfied with this set up, but some of the employees are satisfied with this arrangement because they are doing their work-related activities in their home even when they are not physically present at their workplace. WFH and employee job satisfaction are interconnected because it allows employees to manage their own time as long as they carry out their duties and responsibilities well. Furthermore, WFH virtually eliminates the constant supervision and emotional and social interaction with colleagues or supervisors that is associated with office work, and as a result, the importance of job autonomy in the minds of home workers has been weakened. This kind of work setup is very convenient for employees whose homes are far from their offices. Thorstensson, E. (2020) mentioned in his study that a lot of employees prefer the work from setup for it saves them in commuting to the office, which can be very time consuming, as they can get stuck in heavy traffics especially during rush hours. Because of this, employees have more free time to spend with their families and friends. Employees benefit from remote working because of increased autonomy and the decreased commute time which will help the employees to have a work-life balance. In a study conducted by Costa et al. (2012) it is said that commuting to work, especially during rush hours, has been linked to higher levels of psychological stress, and more physical and mental health concerns. The researcher also added that stress associated with commuting further exacerbates sleep issues, mental health issues, and family and social problems.

Ever since the transition to work-from-home, many employees have acclaimed how convenient it is to be able to work independently and on their own schedules, in addition to all the other benefits of working from home. However, when looking at a different perspective, there are still several drawbacks to this kind of setup most especially to the well-being of the employees which can then affect their work performance. There are advantages and disadvantages to everything in the world, and working remotely is no exception.

According to Xiao et al. (2021), the transition to the work-from-home setup has resulted in a decline in both the physical and well-being of the workers. Since employees are advised to stay and work at home, they become prone to engage in unhealthy eating habits, physical inactivity, lack of communication with coworkers, and difficulties concentrating. Due to these factors, many workers mentioned having physical and mental health issues.

Working from home has a lot of excellent outcomes, according to Oakman et al. (2020), including greater career and family connections, reduced weariness, and increased productivity. Moreover, the confusion of physical and institutional boundaries between work and home can also have a negative impact on an individual's mental and physical health as a result of extended working hours, an insufficiency of or ambiguous differentiation between home and workplace, and a lack of support from employers and other institutions. This complicated scenario necessitates a comprehensive investigation to determine the influence of organizational, physical, environmental, and psychological elements on the mental and physical health of those who are required to comply with Work From Home regulations.

While it is imperative to take into consideration all of the advantages and disadvantages of the work from home setup and how it can affect the employees' performance and well-being, Esra et al. (2020) emphasized in their study that the productivity of those who work from home still highly depends on how their organization handles the situation and how they can meet the needs of their employee during the work from home setup. The equipment and the internet connection that they will be using must be provided by the company and it is also their primary obligation to make sure that all of their employees' physical, mental, and emotional needs are being met.

Methodology

Research Design

The Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) method was employed in this study, a very efficient methodology for examining topics that are quite complex, ambiguous, and vague (Pain, 2015).

Participants

The data that was acquired by the researchers, was gathered through the use of purposive sampling to come up with a final sample of seven participants. In purposive sampling, the participants are chosen based on their relevance to the research issue in nonprobability sampling since the goal is to get a deeper knowledge rather than to generalize to a larger population (Neuman, 2000).

Instrument

The researchers interviewed the participants through Zoom with a researcher made questionnaire containing open-ended interview questions regarding their work from home experiences. The first part of the interview contained questions regarding the participants' biography while the second part contained open-ended questions with regard to how the work from home setup affects the participant's productivity and overall well-being.

Procedure

The researchers conducted an interview of the participants through a Zoom meeting to comply with safety measures during this pandemic, and add the fact that the primary respondents for this study are Work From Home workers in Metro Manila. The researchers constructed questions that fit the criteria and have a clear goal in getting the scope of how WFH has implications on productivity and well-being.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to data collection, participants were provided with comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. This informed consent process ensured that participants had a clear understanding of their involvement and gave their voluntary agreement to participate. Moreover, participants' personal information was treated with utmost confidentiality. The researchers assured them that their identities would remain anonymous throughout the study. By anonymizing the data during analysis and reporting, the researchers further protected the participants' privacy and ensured their sensitive information would not be disclosed.

Results and Discussion

Majority of the response of the participants resulted in six major themes which are the advantages of work from home, disadvantages of work from home, challenges of working from home, solutions to challenges experienced while working from home, workplace productivity while working from home, impact of work from home on well-being and the importance of having dedicated workplace at home. The following statements summarize the findings of the research grounded on the questions raised in the statement of the problem.

Table 1.

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Advantages of work from home	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Convenience 2. Flexible schedule 3. Cost Efficient/Money Saving 4. Greater Work Productivity 5. Efficient Time use
Disadvantages of working from home	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inadequate Technical and Office Equipment 2. Isolation and less workplace connection 3. Blurring of Boundaries between work and home
Solutions to challenges experienced while working from home	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Setting and sticking to a routine 2. Establishing a functional workspace at home 3. Seeking help when needed 4. Minimizing distractions 5. Ensuring clear and strong boundaries work-life boundaries 6. Maintaining teammate/workmate communication 7. Taking scheduled rest breaks 8. Practicing self-care
Workplace productivity when working from home	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Productivity levels improved because there was enough time for mental and physical relaxation 2. Work outputs increased due to flexible hours 3. Productivity levels declined when micromanaged
Impact of work from home on well-being	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Greater well-being due to increased feelings of satisfaction, enjoyment, fulfillment, and motivation 2. Improved well-being due to increased amount of time spent with families, with relaxation and self-care.
Importance of having a dedicated workspace at home	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increases focus and concentration at work 2. Helps minimize distractions 3. Ensures privacy 4. Allows for efficient monitoring of tasks and workloads

Advantages of Work From Home

To define the theme of benefits of working from home, it can be best recognized as the characteristics that satisfy the employees' well-being and their productivity toward their work, which are convenient in the sense that time isn't wasted because of traffic, there is more flexibility in time spent working, and as well as practical for there is no longer the need to spend for transportation.

When working from home, participants stated the scenarios that describe the benefits of working from home:

"Great experience and opportunity for us, employees, to spend more time with our families, to relax and enjoy every bit of it." (P7)

"More time sa family at syempre nakakatipid talaga." (More time to spend with family and of course it is more practical.) (P2)

Participants also suggested how working from home was convenient:

"Uhm bali for me mas convenient kasi nasa bahay lang. Mas malaking yung natitipid kasi di na namamasahi," (For me, it was more convenient because you get to stay at home. It also saves me money since I don't have to pay for transportation.) (P4)

The results have shown that most of the employees who participated in the study reported that working from home has several benefits including it is more convenient, flexible schedule, cost efficient/money saving, greater work productivity and efficient time use. This can be supported by the study of Mokhtar (2020), in which the researcher discovered that there are major advantages of work from home wherein while working from home it can save money because no transportation is required to get to work also it can save time. Additionally, working from home it can give more time to spend with family, it can lessen the pressure and it increase productivity. Work from home can give a time flexibility because it can play the role of being a parent, son and also as an employee. (Abiddin et al., 2022)

The findings in the present study are consistent with the findings of Thorstensson, E. (2020) who said that type of work environment is particularly suitable for employees whose residences are far away from their workplaces. He found that many workers prefer working from home since it saves them time on their commutes, which can be quite time-consuming when they get trapped in traffic, especially during rush hour.

As a result, workers have more free time to spend with their loved ones. Reyes and Carlier (2021) supported this claim as per the researchers, employees gain from remote work since it gives them more freedom and reduces their commuting time, which will help them be more productive and the need for work-life balance among employees. Additionally, according to the research, both employees and employers have applauded the ability to work from home for improving work-life balance. The WFH arrangement gives employees

more freedom by allowing them to do their tasks and activities away from the office, having the freedom to decide how to balance work and personal life, as well as where to work.

Disadvantages of Working From Home

To narrate the theme of disadvantages of working from home, it can be acknowledged as the variables that affect the well-being and the productivity of the employees. These are the feelings of isolation and less workplace connection, blurring of boundaries between work, inadequate technical and office equipment and curbing the tendency to work too much as the participants describe.

Although the participants on this current study are from various field of work, majority of the participants have experienced the same challenges of working at this setup full-time. As the participants worked from home, they described the disadvantage of working from home:

"uh medyo mahirap sa WFH, wala kang nakikitang ibang tao, wala kang nakakausap so medyo boring in a part, na wala kang peers or officemate" (It was difficult, working from home, you don't get to see other people, you don't get to talk to them personally so it was a little bit boring because you don't have peers or officemate.)

In some instances, the full-time work-from-home employees of this study have a varying work home challenges, as some factors may also affect its occurrences such as their marital status and household dynamic. One participant who happens to be mother have experienced a more laborious work-from-home experience as this setup can be demanding especially when they would also have to cater the households' needs while they are working.

The participant mentioned that work from home can be exhausting:

"I've been really tired and exhausted because I multitask everything now, taking care of my baby, doing household chores, and doing my work. I didn't have enough time to rest or take a nap, and it causes me headaches." (P5)

This is consistent with the study that was conducted by Galanti et al. (2021). The previous study has determined that being around family members, especially those who have toddlers to take care of, can be disadvantageous as it can hinder them from being able to perform their work duties. Working from home has also resulted in blurring the lines and boundaries between work and home. Participants now have to do work responsibilities, while also catering to the needs of the household, which can really be quite exhausting to their part.

The participants expressed what the challenges are from working at home:

"Mahirap kasi through chat lang nag uusap usap ganon kasi syempre kapag chat di maiiwasan yung misunderstanding" (It was uncompromising because the only way to communicate was through chat and of course through that method you can never avoid misunderstanding.) (P4)

They also described that technology was one of the challenges for this kind of setup:

"naranasan ko dito is yung mawalan ka ng kuryente, nawawala for 2 days." (I experienced (at home) where there was no power, it was gone for 2 days.) (P7)

"Since our internet connection wasn't that strong compared to the office" (P1)

Lack of proper communication with coworkers has been indicated as some of the disadvantages of the work from home setup (Nakrošienė, 2019). It has been determined that due to the lack of interaction with colleagues, the employees are more likely to experience stress for it can be challenging for them to be able to communicate especially if it's only through online messaging platform. This also further demonstrate how imperative for employees to have a reliable work equipment and a stable internet connection for them to not only do their work efficiently but also to be able to communicate and collaborate well with their coworkers.

The present study is consistent with the previous studies conducted by Reyes et al. (2021). Previous researchers have determined that the work-from-home setup has blurred lines that separate work life and personal life, and thus, provide difficulties for workers to maintain a work-life balance. The research showed that overworking of employees working at home is frequent since, the majority of the time, there is always a need for them to extend their work hours resulting in a poorer work-life balance and emotional exhaustion.

A previous study has also stated that social isolation and not having social interaction have been indicated as one of main disadvantages of the work-from-home setup. It is also said that employees find it difficult for them to communicate if it is not face-to-face for it is prone to miscommunication. It is said in the existing literature that, when people use online messaging networks to address difficulties, they experience more psychological stress and worry which can lead to a negative impact on employees' mental health (Chen, 2021).

The participants of the present study have also mentioned this as one of the disadvantages of the work-from-home setup, stating that not having peers or workmates and physical connection makes it challenging to be able to work on their assigned tasks as it can hinder their communication, especially in terms of task-related concerns. In line with this, not having the right tools and equipment such as having a reliable internet connection and advanced computers or laptops that can handle multiple workloads, can also serve as a disadvantage when it comes to working at home (Esra, 2020).

Solutions to Challenges Experienced While Working From Home

To further illustrate the theme of solutions to challenges experienced while working from home, it can be described as methods to solve challenges that the participants have encountered while working from home. The following are the solutions used in encountering challenges: setting and sticking to a routine, establishing a functional workspace at home, seeking help when needed, minimizing distractions, ensuring clear and strong boundaries work-life boundaries, maintaining teammate/workmate communication, taking scheduled rest breaks, and practicing self-care.

The participants mentioned the solutions they used in encountering challenges while working at home:

"Lahat ng alam kong gagawin ko for example paglilinis ng bahay, pagluluto at pagsasaing ginagawa ko na muna sya lahat bago ako pumasok sa workplace ko" (Everything that I know I need to do for example cleaning the house and cooking in general. I do it all before I start to work.) (P2)

They also described making a list to accomplish before work helped in solving challenges they encountered:

"Kailangan meron akong to-do list" (I need to have a to-do list.) (P1)

"I separate myself from things that could easily distract me, like social media and such" (P3).

They also illustrated that avoiding distractions are useful strategies to be productive:

"I avoid using my personal gadgets. tapos ayun, I also keep a note of the urgent tasks for the day to make sure nothing important slips out of priority" (I avoid using my personal gadgets. Then, I also keep a note of the urgent tasks for the day to make sure nothing important slips out of priority.) (P4)

The participants also mentioned prioritizing the work assigned is very helpful in being productive:

"Prioritizing your tasks, list down tasks that need to be done immediately up to the easiest or the lightest task." (P5)

Employees who work from home, feel more alone and isolated when there is a lack of social interaction. Loneliness is detrimental to both physical and emotional health and might lower your performance. Leaders should make sure that distant employees have the resources necessary to deal with the difficulties of loneliness (Gurchiek, 2021). Try to schedule social activities apart from work that will provide you with the social interaction you demand if you work from home. Naturally, follow local COVID-19 safety regulations while doing this. Try working in a coworking space or library, or schedule regular video calls with family and friends.

Everyone could become frustrated by a weak internet connection or outdated equipment. Ensure that the employees of your work group have all they require to connect from home as a team leader. Leaders have to ensure that their employees have access to the most recent versions of the programs and apps they use (Skirka, 2020). They could even want to think about paying for their team's internet expenses so they can purchase the quickest connection possible. Having their personal gadgets on hand can be beneficial if they work remotely and need a backup in case their business computer breaks down. Also, an effort to find a nearby with good network connectivity that they may use during an emergency.

Workplace Productivity When Working From Home

For workplace productivity when working from home, it can be related to variables that affect the productivity of the participants while working from home. The following are the impacts of working from home on productivity: productivity levels improved because there was enough time for mental and physical relaxation, work outputs increased due to flexible hours, and productivity levels declined when micromanaged.

As the participants observed, they described the impacts of work from home on productivity:

"You can work several hours earlier than your assigned shift, and you can even extend your hours if you think you have slacked too much during your shift." (P7)

They also noted that having flexibility impacted their productivity while working from home:

"I can multi-task because of the flexibility of my time." (P6)

These responses from the participants showed that the WFH setup gives flexible working hours in which employees can have the power to manage their time and to juggle different tasks at the same time. Thus, flexible working hours can be viewed as a key determiner in the ability of the participants to work productively in working from home. According to Castrillon (2022), the flexible working arrangements allow employees to have the opportunity to decide when they want to work. Employees benefit from it by having the freedom to work during the time that they feel more productive, unlike working in the office wherein the start and the end of their working hours are predetermined, accompanied by workplace interruptions and supervisions. The participants also mentioned the difference in their productivity when they're working onsite as compared to when they are working at home, stating that they are more able to work productively at home for there's no presence of supervisors who micromanage their employees:

"Kasi pag-onsite, I have the pressure of, parang nandun yung pressure na mag perform sa trabaho, lagi mo nakikita yung mga supervisors mo, palagi kang pinagsasabihan, pag mataas AHT (call handle time) mo, real time ka na-cacallout, pero pag dating sa WFH, mas makapag-focus ka lang muna sa work, kaya feel ko mas nag-improve yung productivity ko, kaya mas nakapag-step up ako pag WFH." (P4)

This can be supported by a phenomenological study conducted by Castillo (2018), in which it was found that micromanagement is adverse for organizational productivity. Majority of the participants conveyed feelings of discomfort and distress when being controlled and observed by micromanaging leaders.

Impacts of Work From Home on Well-Being

This theme is defined by the participants as the effects on the well-being of the participants while working from home, and these are as follows: greater well-being due to increased feelings of satisfaction, enjoyment, fulfillment, and motivation and, improved well-being due to the increased amount of time spent with families, with relaxation and self-care.

The participants expressed what are the impacts of work from home on well-being:

"Great experience and opportunity for us, employees, to spend more time with our families, to relax and enjoy every bit of it" (P6)

They also mentioned that it was relaxing:

"This work-from-home setup affects my overall well-being positively" (P2)

This theme is consistent with the study of Benita et al. (2020) where they found out that employees tend to do more during the work-from-home set up. It is said that you can meet both work demands and family demands at the same time while being productive at work. Because of this, they have more time to unwind and deal with their obligations without too much pressure.

Importance of Having Dedicated Workspace at Home

The importance of having a workspace at home, can be described as the significance of having a workspace at home and these are as follows: increases focus and concentration at work, helps minimize distractions, ensures privacy, and allows for efficient monitoring of tasks and workloads

The participants mentioned the importance of having your own workspace at home.

" Important talaga yung space sa pagwo-work from home kasi syempre pag nandyan yung personal space mo, mas mapu-push yung sarili mo na mas maging productive" (It really is important to have your own space when working from home because when you have your own personal space, you can motivate yourself to be more productive.) (P7)

They also pointed out that privacy equates to a better performance:

" Having your own working space really helps to focus your mind on your work." (P5)

It is said that the participants tend to be more productive and have more motivation to do work when they are alone and also less distractions when they have personal space in the workplace. According to Awada et al. (2021), productivity was positively impacted by improved mental and physical health and having a dedicated workspace. The general perception of their study was that workers who had their own personal space at home had higher levels of productivity than those who did not. It also proves that workers are less productive when they share with other members of the family or peers.

There is a strong relationship between a well-arranged working environment and an efficient workplace. Well-arranged workplace can be considered as low noise levels, appropriate temperature that can increase productivity. In addition, according to Okuyan et al (2021), working from home and having a personal space has conditions not only to decrease the health issues or spreading the virus but also the improvement on productivity of individuals.

The results of the present study have shown the importance of having a dedicated workspace at home in order to focus and concentrate at work, minimize distractions, ensure privacy, and have efficient monitoring of tasks and workloads – which is highly consistent with the previous study conducted by Donnelly and Proctor-Thomson in 2015. Although the previous study has also stated that in order to ensure the effectiveness of the work-from-home setup, it is necessary to make an extra effort to educate family members about the new work-from-home setup. Dependent children and elderly parents may need to be made aware of this setup so they don't expect the employee to handle household duties during work hours. Setting up a workplace in a private area may be the best course of action to minimize the distraction of other people's presence at home (Baruch et al., 2017).

A previous study has also determined that having a dedicated space at home when working can result to a higher level of productivity than those who have to share space with family members. It has been found out that there is a strong relationship between a well arranged working environment and an efficient workplace (Awada, 2021).

The factors that prompt challenges to employees' overall well-being and productivity are the lack of gadgets and resources and physical interaction in the workplace. It will be challenging to work at home when one cannot buy devices and office equipment; some employees might need help to catch up with the latest technologies. Another thing would be keeping social interaction with fellow workmates. Interacting with people personally is much easier than doing it digitally; there will be fewer chances of miscommunication. This means that personal interaction and complete resources will motivate employees to work in balance and harmony. They can build strong relationships and work to their full potential.

Working from home has positive effects on employee well-being. It can increase satisfaction, enjoyment, excitement, motivation to work, relaxation, self-awareness, and positivity. Working from home enables employees to work at their own pace. Thus, it positively affects their well-being, work motivation, and productivity. However, the WFH setup can also have negative impacts on employees. A lack of resources and less social interaction can make employees feel anxious and isolated. This demonstrates that, despite the majority of participants positive responses, the WFH setup has a negative impact on some employees. It implies that only some experience the exact effects of the WFH setup on their well-being. Regarding productivity, working from home, depending on the arrangement, can be a more productive setting than the typical enclosed environment, resulting in a better job and life balance.

Working from home offers a lot of advantages for employees. There's less wasted time, more flexibility in working pace, and more practical, so there is no longer a need to spend for transportation. Working from home is more convenient for everyone because it allows employees to work productively without going to physical offices. It also helps to save money because employees are not required to pay for gasoline or transportation fare. Thus, a work-from-home setup is beneficial not only for employees and employers but also for the environment. There's less transportation, which means fewer greenhouse gases. Work-from-home arrangements should be encouraged or implemented in corporate offices as they will bring convenience to the employees and the environment.

Disadvantages are variables that negatively affect employee well-being and productivity. Working from home can increase the chance for employees to feel isolated, decrease workplace connection, and complicate work and life matters. WFH setup also requires employees to have their equipment for work, which will be a burden for some employees. Although other employers sponsor their employees' equipment, it's still challenging since employees don't get to interact with their workmates personally. Working from home can also be exhausting for employees that multitask their personal and work-related matters. There are quite a few disadvantages when having a WFM setup. However, despite these challenges, it will still be convenient and efficient for everyone at the end of the day.

Employee performance can be influenced by their work environment. The most common challenges brought about by the WFH setup were a need for more resources and tools that a standard office can provide, ensuring effective remote collaboration, and resolving technical difficulties. Aside from that, it was challenging to maximize productivity, deal with isolation, and have less workplace interaction. Work-from-home distractions frequently cause these difficulties. It was also uncompromising because the only way to communicate was via chat, which can cause miscommunications. Technology and electricity were also environmental factors. Some employees experience power outages that last for hours or days, which can affect their productivity and workload.

Conclusions

The work-from-home setup has both positive and negative impacts on employees. It gives employees a convenient working environment that allows them to work flexibly. However, employees also tend to experience feelings of isolation and technical equipment insufficiency in this setup. Employees tend to be more productive in a WFH setup. The flexible working hours from the setup is really helpful in allowing employees to have sufficient time for themselves. Physical and mental relaxation is indeed important because it increases the work capacity of employees. The current study has also determined how imperative it is for employees to have a dedicated work space when in this setup for it allows them to be able to concentrate more on their tasks.

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